

ADOPTION OF VIRTUAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF TRENDS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

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Abstract. *The study performs a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) adoption research from 2001 to 2024 to map the intellectual landscape, identify emerging trends, and guide future research directions in this rapidly evolving field by addressing several research questions. This was done through bibliometric analysis. The Scopus database was searched for relevant documents published between 2001 and 2024, and data were extracted from this source. Biblioshiny, VOSviewer, and R-Studio were used for analysis. The PRISMA protocol was followed to ensure methodological rigour and reproducibility. Analysis showed a 14.61% annual growth rate in publications, with a significant acceleration from 2017-2024. Six research clusters were identified: virtual learning delivery, immersive technologies, higher education practices, e-learning platforms, pedagogical approaches, and assessment tools. Publication volume and impact were significantly uneven across geography, with selective publishers attaining higher citation rates. The implication of this is that the field has evolved from infrastructure-focused studies to user-centered approaches with artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and learning analytics. This study is restricted to English language publications and Scopus database coverage.*

Keywords: *virtual Learning Environment; Technology Adoption; Bibliometric Analysis; Educational Technology; E-Learning*

INTRODUCTION

The virtual learning environments (VLEs) adoption has become an essential factor in modern education. Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs) are key to education as it helps in sharing educational materials, fostering teamwork, and dealing with administrative chores. VLEs have improved student participation and learning results through personal learning tools, media, and data tracking. This demonstrates that understanding VLE adoption is important to ensure how these features can be efficiently utilized to make education even more effective.

Technology acceptance is one of the main factors influencing technology adoption (Athambawa et al., 2023). The VLE is used for other different functions such as student admission, course registration, and administrative purposes. Online learning platforms are continuously being adopted by higher education institutions (Athambawa et al., 2023) with emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, virtual and augmented reality, and learning analytics, which are used to improve learner engagement and learning effectiveness. On this note, Zahrae et al. (2024) revealed AI technologies, such as machine learning and deep learning, to adapt learning experiences

in VLEs. Furthermore, previous studies had been conducted on VLEs use in several administrative functions to improve student recruitment and resource assignments (Nurhasanah et al., 2024).

With the rise of pandemic induced e-learning market transformation, revenue is expected to increase by \$830 billion between 2022 and 2027 (Himanshubagdi et al., 2023). Consequently, VLE adoption has grown in strategic and financial importance. However, this shift also suggests that an understanding of user adoption behavioral factors must be considered an important component of implementing VLEs for educational continuity and equity in various contexts. Although these have been recognized as necessary, few comprehensive studies have been conducted on adoption trends, thematic evolution, or future directions in this area. This gap must be addressed to advance scholarly knowledge and maximize the deployment of VLEs in educational settings.

However, owing to the rapid growth and adoption of VLEs, their importance in education cannot be underestimated, and the factors affecting VLE effectiveness must be appropriately understood as an effective instructional design tool. This study fills the current research gaps by examining VLE adoption trends and determining the key behavioral and technological factors that influence the successful adoption of VLEs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent studies have revealed that research on VLEs has increased exponentially over the past two decades. It has become vital in the communication, collaboration, and interaction of educational systems worldwide (Dayag & Faramarzi, 2024). In primary investigations, technical issues such as infrastructure and functionality were investigated to support traditional instruction in VLEs (Zhao et al., 2024).

In addition to that, research conducted at Ghana's College of Education has revealed that technology helps improve teaching approaches (KofiMpuangnan, 2024). However, the focus of that study had been on integrating pedagogical frameworks and instructional strategies into technology. It can be seen that this progression matches some of the theories and models that have previously been established, including the diffusion of innovations (DOI), technology organization environment framework (TOE), technology acceptance models (TAM, TAM2, TAM3), as well as the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT and UTAUT2), which are structured frameworks that are used to understand the adoption and optimal implementation of new technologies in educational settings (Athambawa et al., 2022).

The development of a customized educational experience is proposed by integrating artificial intelligence/driven learning analytics and immersive technology such as virtual and augmented reality. Previous study highlighted that Virtual and Augmented Reality combined with Artificial Intelligence can transform education. Building on these findings, educational experiences show that synergy dramatically improves students' motivation, memory retention, and understanding (Balushi et al., 2024).

This proves that an increasing number of people realize that new technologies must be paired with user-friendly designs and efficient teaching methods. Nevertheless, gaps exist, including insufficient long-term studies, lack of analyses of the role of behavioral factors in VLE adoption, and lack of uniformity in the geographic focus of the research. While many research had been conducted on digital tools and platforms in education, insights are limited to a few regions. Key questions such as accessibility, adaptability, and equity have not been sufficiently explored. Although these studies span a wide range of field, there are still limitation on the effective use of

these technologies. Additionally, few novel investigations have addressed these persistent challenges in this area, and progress towards more inclusive and effective solutions has been hindered.

However, studies across different regions have shown that integrating digital tools into the educational context is a persistent challenge (Satiman & Zulkifli, 2022; Awang et al., 2022; Kumarasamy et al., 2023). This understanding was further extended by Rashid et al. (2021), who presented a comprehensive overview of issues, particularly in the Southeast Asian context. Gunasinghe et al. (2019) highlighted the constraints in Sri Lanka, and Gautam et al. (2021) provided insights into Bhutan's context and earlier work by Dhakal (2016) in Nepal. Camilleri (2020) examined the dynamics in Southern Europe, notably Malta, whereas Farrelly et al. (2018) had conducted research on Irish-specific perspective. Based on these studies' findings, comparable issues can be seen in two different European regions. This global discourse was furthered by Santana-Mancilla et al. (2019), who explored issues present in Mexico.

Existing research on the adoption of a Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) has revealed considerable geographical imbalances and challenges that vary dramatically across regions. Bibliometric studies have been performed in various scientific fields. However, there is a lack of thorough research that identifies the synthesis of research trends, thematic clusters, and high-impact contributions in VLE adoption by 2024. However, across the studies, it has been proven that developed and developing countries face a global issue in regard of VLE use in education.

This study aims to contribute to refined empirical research with a bibliometric analysis of adopting a Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) and a systematic literature review. The study outlines six Research Questions (RQs) through a thorough bibliometric analysis.

This study offers new perspectives on the future of VLE. A longitudinal analysis of publication trends highlighted the shift in the field from infrastructure studies to user-centered approaches. Moreover, applying bibliometric laws reveals the laws of scientific productivity and influence of high-quality research, thus providing a solid basis for evaluating innovation in this field. This study bridges existing gaps by emphasizing user adaptation, cross-cultural comparisons, and the integration of advanced technologies. It also provides strategic recommendations for optimizing VLE adoption and implementation.

In addition, this study endeavours to contribute refined empirical insights by adopting bibliometric analysis to evaluate the existing body of knowledge comprehensively. In alignment with this objective, this study addresses the following six research questions (RQs) through meticulous and thorough analyses.

RQ1. What are the descriptive characteristics of refined empirical research on Virtual Learning Environment adoption?

RQ2. What are the trends in annual scientific publications on Virtual Learning Environment Adoption?

RQ3. What are the most relevant and high-impact sources of adoption of Virtual Learning Environments?

RQ4. What are the most relevant countries in the adoption of virtual learning environments?

RQ5. What are the outcomes of Bradford's Law of Scattering and Lotka's Law of Scientific Productivity?

RQ6. What are the trending research avenues for future research on adopting virtual learning environments?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employs a sophisticated methodological framework of bibliometric analysis approach executed through three interconnected phases. The data collection and screening phase leveraged the Scopus databases, encompassing publications from 2001 to 2024 with a worldwide geographical scope, while adhering rigorously to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) protocol to ensure methodological transparency and reproducibility. The PRISMA statement was initially developed to address inadequate reporting in systematic reviews and meta-analyses, providing a checklist and flow diagram to guide authors in reporting their research comprehensively (Yusuff, 2023). The research used the Preferred Reporting Items for Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) and Systematic Reviews statement to define the study design. Sarkis-Onofre et al. (2021) stated that the PRISMA statement is meant to assist authors in increasing the reporting of systematic literature reviews and meta-analyses.

The software selection phase incorporated a complementary suite of analytical tools: robust bibliometric analysis was performed using Biblioshiny software operating through R-Studio, VOSviewer, and R-Studio Program for statistical computations, and Microsoft Excel for data cleaning and preliminary analysis. The data analysis stage was systematically divided into quantitative and qualitative stages. Quantitative analysis included bibliometric analysis techniques, descriptive information analysis, and scientific production analysis, including thematic evolution analysis, Lotka's Law of Scientific Productivity Analysis, source impact analysis, Bradford's Law of Scattering Analysis, keyword co-occurrence analysis, trend topic analysis, and thematic mapping of keywords. The comprehensive methodological architecture of this study allowed for a detailed study of the literature landscape from macro-level bibliometric viewpoints to micro-level thematic interpretations, thereby establishing a solid and methodologically sound analysis framework in line with current scholarly standards. Figure 1 summarizes the research methodology.

Figure 1: Summary of the research methodology used. Methodology according to (Amarathunga et al., 2024).

3.1. Data Collection and Screening

The initial step in conducting a bibliometric study involves defining a clear and well-established goal, which is crucial for selecting the most appropriate analysis methodology and data format for effective data collection (Amarathunga et al., 2024; Jatnika et al., 2024; Donthu et al., 2021). The Scopus database is one of the largest databases for scientific abstracts and citations, containing around 50 million articles of literature since 1823 (Amarathunga et al., 2023; Alzard et al., 2022). An integrated analytical framework combines quantitative and qualitative methods to examine bibliometric data holistically.

The search strategy framework was applied rigorously to the systematic review protocol to investigate Virtual Learning Environment adoption using Scopus as the primary data repository. The search parameters were comprehensively defined using the following scope and coverage specifications: search in the database (Scopus), search field (All), temporal bounds (2001-2024), and language restriction (English). The search string was precisely constructed using the Boolean operators: "Virtual Learning Environment" AND adoption AND PUBYEAR > 2000 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")).

Data extraction was performed on November 12, 2024, with 254 documents ($n = 254$) as the initial corpus. The records were screened strictly according to predefined inclusion/exclusion criteria, and no records were removed ($n = 0$) during the quality assessment phase. Consequently, the final dataset comprising 254 documents was retained for comprehensive bibliometric analysis, with the original document pool intact.

The methodological framework was operationalized using several interconnected phases. First, the Scopus database was chosen because of its extensive coverage of scholarly literature and well-established reliability in bibliometric research. A systematic search strategy was developed to address the research focus comprehensively and precisely. A systematic review was conducted using the PRISMA model to document the review process following methodological transparency and reproducibility. Data preparation and quality control were performed using specialized software tools. R-Studio was used for data preprocessing, Biblioshiny was used for bibliometric analysis, and VOSviewer was used for network visualization.

This systematic approach helped to analyze quantitative and qualitative analytical dimensions. An integrated analytical framework was developed that enables a nuanced understanding of the literature while maintaining methodological rigor consistent with established bibliometric practices (Zakaria et al., 2021; Moher et al., 2009). The study design shows the process of "identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion," which is presented in Figure 2. A collection of documents was selected using inclusion and exclusion criteria, followed by systematic extraction.

3.2. Software Selection

The Bibliometrix R package, Biblioshiny, is a complete bibliometric analysis tool. Citation, co-citation, and keyword co-occurrence analyses were performed and thematic maps and network graphs were generated. This package benefits researchers who require detailed bibliometric studies and the visualization of their results (Fu et al., 2023; Rani et al., 2022). Further, bibliometric networks were built using VOSviewer to visualize the evolution of research trends. For example, it has been used to chart research trends in multi-input transfer function studies, such as the top countries and thematic clusters that are dominant in that field (PutriIndriati et al., 2024).

Biblioshiny and VOSviewer were selected due to their user-friendly interface, detailed visualization capabilities and robust analytical features. Microsoft Excel was utilized to support data cleaning and quality assessment, while R-Studio was utilized to maintain formatting and to facilitate integration with Biblioshiny. The study conducted a complete data evaluation and visualized bibliometric relationships through a synergistic combination of software tools.

Figure 2: Flow diagram of the search strategy.
Source: (Zakaria et al., 2021; Moher, 2019).

3.3. Data Analysis

An integrated analytical framework combining quantitative and qualitative methods was used to holistically examine the bibliometric data. Data were organized into a CSV format to ensure systematic analysis. R-Studio was used to prepare pre-analysis data to make it compatible with Biblioshiny and VOSviewer. This multi-phase, integrated approach allowed this study to discover nuanced insights into publication patterns, author contributions, research themes, and emerging trends.

Quantitative and qualitative methods were integrated to thoroughly analyze bibliometric data through an integrated analytical framework. The data were carefully organized in the CSV format for systematic analysis. R-Studio was used for the pre-analysis data preparation to make it compatible with Biblioshiny and VOSviewer. This integrated multi-phase approach enabled this study to uncover nuanced insights into publication patterns, author contributions, research themes, and emerging trends.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RQ1. What are the descriptive characteristics of refined empirical research on Virtual Learning Environment adoption?

4.1 Descriptive features of the extracted data

Document Characteristics	
Timespan	2001:2024
Documents	254
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	200
Annual Growth Rate %	14.61
Document Average Age	7.73
Average citations per doc	18.03
References	8259
Keyword Analysis	
Keywords Plus (ID)	1273
Author's Keywords (DE)	699
Author Collaboration and Metrics	
Authors	709
Authors of single-authored docs	27
Authors of multiple -authored docs	682
Single-authored docs	30
Multiple-authored docs	224
Co-Authors per Doc	3.04
International co-authorships %	20.08
Document Types	
article	109
book	1
book chapter	14
conference paper	94
conference review	18
note	2
review	15

Table 1: Descriptive features of the extracted data
Source(s): Output of Biblioshiny software

Table 1 presents a detailed analysis of these descriptive features. Based on the findings of this study, 254 documents authored by 709 contributors, originating from 200 sources and published between 2001 and 2024, were extracted from the Scopus database. Among these, 30 were single-authored publications and 224 involved multiple authors, yielding a collaboration index of 20.08%. The documents collectively incorporated 8,259 references, with an average citation rate of 18.03 per document, indicating a strong citation impact in the literature on Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) adoption. The analysis further revealed a yearly growth rate of 14.61%, reflecting increasing interest in the field over the specified period. Regarding document type, the dataset included 109 articles, 94 conference papers, 15 reviews, and several other types, illustrating the diversity of scholarly contributions. Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the descriptive features.

RQ2. What are the trends in annual scientific publications on Virtual Learning Environment Adoption?

Figure 3. The Annual Scientific Publications 2001–2024
Source(s): Output of Biblioshiny Software

The findings showed that the number of publications has gradually improved and literature quality has increased significantly over the past year. Figure 3 shows the annual scientific publications from 2001 to 2024 of VLE adoption. The findings revealed a notable evolutionary pattern in publication trends for Virtual Learning environment adoption research, demonstrating significant growth in scholarly contributions over the examined period. Annual scientific production from 2001 to 2024 exhibits a clear upward trajectory with distinct developmental phases. As illustrated in Figure 3, the field showed modest activity in its early years (2001-2005), with one to four annual publications. However, since 2006, research interest has accelerated substantially, marked by a steady increase in the number of publications. The field experienced particularly significant growth during 2017-2024, reaching its peak of 23 publications in 2024. Notable surges in research output occurred in 2021-2022, maintaining a consistent level of 22 publications annually, followed by a brief decline to 12 publications in 2023 before reaching its highest point. This publication pattern suggests increasing scholarly attention to the adoption of Virtual Learning environments, particularly in recent years. The analysis revealed an annual growth rate of approximately 14.61% over the entire period, with a particularly robust growth rate of 10.43% observed in the last five years (2019-2024), indicating the field's expanding research landscape and growing academic significance.

Figure 4. Thematic evolution map
Source(s): Output of Biblioshiny Software

Figure 4 illustrates the thematic evolution of Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) research from 2001 to 2024, depicting shifts across three periods: 2001–2013, 2014–2020, and 2021–2024. In the Sankey diagram, the nodes represent subjects, and size represent the number of keywords. The nodes connecting line indicate how the study focus has transformed over time, with different themes revealed in different other colors. The width of the line indicates the number of shared keywords; wider lines signify more significant connections between two topics (Amarathunga et al., 2024). Between 2001 and 2013, 'virtual learning environments' emerged as the dominant foundational theme shaping subsequent research pathways. This was followed by 'virtual reality,' along with 'learning environments' and 'learning systems,' which played a comparatively smaller role. While 'commerce' was also present during this period, its influence on the field's evolution remained modest. By 2014–2020, "computer-aided instruction" emerged as a central theme, connecting with both earlier and later themes and introducing specialized areas such as "learning" and "higher education. For the 2021-2024 period, the analysis demonstrates a continuation of 'computer-aided instruction' emphasizing learning systems and behavioral research, alongside significant developments in 'e-learning' (focusing on technology adoption and teaching) and 'virtual learning environments' (emphasizing engineering education). This period also witnessed an emerging human-centric research direction incorporating virtual reality aspects. The analysis

of thematic evolution revealed new research directions, focusing on behavioral research and technology acceptance models in computer-aided instruction, structural equation modelling approaches in e-learning, engineering education integration in virtual learning environments, and education-focused virtual reality applications in human-centered research.

RQ3. What are the most relevant and high-impact sources of adoption of Virtual Learning Environments?

Sources	Articles
ACM INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE PROCEEDING SERIES	5
COMMUNICATIONS IN COMPUTER AND INFORMATION SCIENCE	5
LECTURE NOTES IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (INCLUDING SUBSERIES LECTURE NOTES IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND LECTURE NOTES IN BIOINFORMATICS)	5
LECTURE NOTES IN NETWORKS AND SYSTEMS	5
PROCEEDINGS OF THE EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON GAMES-BASED LEARNING	5
PROCEEDINGS OF THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON E-LEARNING, ICEL	5
BRITISH JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY	4
IEEE ACCESS	4
F1000RESEARCH	3
IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES	3

Table 2. Most top ten relevant sources in the field of VLE adoption
Source(s): Output of Biblioshiny Software

This study contributes to the field by identifying the most influential publications that have introduced a new potential for VLE adoption through bibliometric analysis and examining the distribution of scholarly journals on Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) adoption across key academic venues. Table 2 presents a quantitative analysis of publication frequencies by source. The findings identified six primary publication platforms, each contributing five publications: the ACM International Conference Proceedings Series, Communications in Computer and Information Science, Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries in Artificial Intelligence and Bioinformatics), Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, Proceedings of the European Conference on Games-Based Learning, and Proceedings of the International Conference on E-Learning (ICEL).

Source	h index	g index	m index	TC
BRITISH JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY	3	4	0.16666667	92
IEEE ACCESS	3	4	0.5	29
IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES	3	3	0.25	51
INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF VIRTUAL AND PERSONAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS	3	3	0.2	25
LECTURE NOTES IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (INCLUDING SUBSERIES LECTURE NOTES IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND LECTURE NOTES IN BIOINFORMATICS)	3	5	0.1875	77
PROCEEDINGS - FRONTIERS IN EDUCATION CONFERENCE, FIE	3	3	0.33333333	26
ACM INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE PROCEEDING SERIES	2	3	0.18181818	10
ADVANCES IN INTELLIGENT SYSTEMS AND COMPUTING	2	2	0.28571429	27
COMMUNICATIONS IN COMPUTER AND INFORMATION SCIENCE	2	3	0.14285714	11
COMPUTERS AND EDUCATION	2	2	0.11764706	676

Table 3. Top ten high-impact sources
Source(s): Output of Biblioshiny Software

Identifying the top ten high-impact sources in VLE adoption research helps researchers focus on the most influential studies and builds on foundational work to advance the field. Table 3 lists the top ten high-impact sources. The British Journal of Educational Technology and IEEE Access follow four publications each, while F1000Research and IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies contribute three. This distribution pattern highlights the predominance of conference proceedings between the top ten sources (60% of top sources) over traditional journals, indicating

a priority for rapid knowledge dissemination in this field. The diversity of sources spans computer science, educational technology, and interdisciplinary venues, thus reflecting the multifaceted nature of VLE research.

The analysis revealed a balanced representation between specialized conferences and high-impact journals, emphasizing the technical and pedagogical aspects of VLE adoption. This distribution aligns with the dynamic nature of the field, where rapid dissemination through conferences and rigorous peer review in established journals play an essential role in advancing knowledge.

The H-index is the highest value of h for which an author or journal has published at least h papers, each of which has been cited at a minimum of h times. Hirsch (2005) introduced the H-index as a metric for quantifying scientific output. The g-index was proposed by Leo Egghe in 2006, and that is the unique most significant number such that the highest g articles together received at least g^2 citations (Egghe, 2006)

In bibliometric analysis, high-impact sources are evaluated using metrics such as the h-index, g-index, m-index, and total citations (TC), which collectively provide insights into academic influence. The data highlight varying patterns of impact across journals. In bibliometric analysis, high-impact sources are evaluated using metrics such as the h-index, g-index, m-index, and total citations (TC), which collectively provide insights into academic influence.

The impact patterns varied across journals, as shown in the data. Six journals (British Journal of Educational Technology, IEEE Access, IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies, International Journal of Virtual and Personal Learning Environments, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, and Proceedings - Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE)) had the highest h-index (3) among the analyzed sources, indicating a balance between the number of publications and the number of citations. Among these, Lecture Notes in Computer Science have the highest g-index (5), which means that the citation performance of this series is concentrated in a few highly cited papers. The performance of Computers and Education in analyzing specific journal performances is exceptional, with high total citations (TC = 676) despite a relatively low h-index (2), indicating the existence of a few articles with strong influence rather than widespread citation impact. On the other hand, IEEE Access achieves the highest m index (0.5), indicating an excellent recent citation performance, but the m index alone does not capture the overall influence or breadth.

These findings highlight the difficulty of interpreting journal impacts using bibliometric metrics. Although traditional indices, such as the h-index, indicate similar performance across the top venues, a deeper analysis shows significant variation in citation patterns. Understanding these distinct aspects of academic influence captured by each index enables researchers to consider multiple metrics holistically to understand how alternative paths can lead to unintended consequences and to make informed decisions about publication strategies and venue selection. A multidimensional bibliometric analysis of order adds a comprehensive framework to measure a journal's impact.

RQ4. What are the most relevant countries in the adoption of virtual learning environments?

Contextual evaluations enhance researchers' understanding of VLE adoption at the national level, enabling meaningful comparisons and identifying research gaps in future studies. In Figure 5, countries shaded in blue color denote those that have conducted studies on VLE adoption. Between these, dark blue shaded countries have published a large number of research on VLE

adoption, while light-blue shaded countries have conducted less research. Countries in gray have no publications on VLE adoption. Table 5 illustrates the top ten countries that contributed to scientific journals.

Figure 5. Scientific productions of the countries
Source(s): Output of Biblioshiny software

Table 4.2. The top ten countries contributed to the scientific publications

Country	Articles	TC	Average article citations
SPAIN	61	860	14.10
NETHERLANDS	04	657	164.25
UNITED KINGDOM	124	558	4.50
USA	141	391	2.77
CANADA	09	256	28.44
SLOVENIA	06	153	25.50
MALAYSIA	51	145	2.84
OMAN	04	126	31.50
TURKEY	06	111	18.50
BOTSWANA	01	93	93.00

Note(s): TC = Total Citations

Source(s): Output of Biblioshiny software

A comprehensive bibliometric analysis of global research output reveals distinctive patterns that merit strategic consideration in scholarly publishing. Notably, the Netherlands' publication profile emerges as a striking example, achieving an exceptional 164.25 citations per article from just four publications, underscoring that impactful research must not be prolific. This contrasts sharply with high-volume producers such as the USA (141 articles) and the UK (124 articles), whose average citations of 2.77 and 4.50 indicate that quantity alone does not guarantee

scholarly impact. Particularly noteworthy are selective publishers, such as Botswana (93 citations per article), Oman, and Canada, each achieving substantial citation impact through focused, high-quality contributions.

These findings suggest that researchers should prioritize comprehensive and methodologically rigorous studies over smaller publications. The data also highlight the value of strategic international collaboration, especially with researchers from high-citation-impact countries. Furthermore, the significant variation in citation impact across regions underscores the opportunities for novel contributions in underexplored areas. For researchers targeting high-impact journals, this analysis emphasizes the importance of developing unique theoretical or methodological contributions that address existing research gaps rather than adopting a volume-based publishing strategy. The success of selective publishers in achieving high citation rates provides compelling evidence that focused high-quality research output is more likely to garner substantial scholarly recognition and impact.

RQ5. What are the outcomes of Bradford's Law of Scattering and Lotka's Law of Scientific Productivity?

Zones	Number of cumulative articles	Number of sources
Core zone (Zone 1)	84	30
Intermediate zone (Zone 2)	87	87
Outlying zone (Zone 3)	83	83
Total	254	200

Table 5. Outcomes of Bradford's law of scattering
Source(s): Output of Biblioshiny software

This study contributes to the field by applying Bradford's law to identify and categorize journals based on their contribution to VLE adoption research. This categorization into core, intermediate, and outlying zones provides valuable insights into the distribution of scholarly literature, highlighting the most influential journals that consistently engage with the subject. This study helps researchers identify core journals, which will help researchers find the most relevant and impactful sources, streamline the literature review process, and guide future research efforts on VLE adoption.

A principle states that the number of scholarly journals in a particular field equals the number of articles in that field. This suggests that a few journals publish a large amount of literature, while many journals publish little. This law is useful for finding core journals of a discipline, helping researchers in locating the most related sources (Sab et al., 2018)

The journals were arranged in descending order according to Bradford's law. This resulted in their classification into three distinct zones: core, intermediate, and outlying. The core zone consists of journals that always publish articles in this field, the intermediate zone consists of journals that sometimes publish articles, and the outlying zone consists of journals that rarely publish articles in this field (Shenton & Hay-Gibson, 2011).

Based on the analysis results in Table 6, the core zone consists of 30 journals that published 84 articles, constituting approximately 33% of the total articles, but slightly deviating from an exact one-third division owing to rounding. These core journals demonstrated consistent engagement with the subject matter. The intermediate zone comprised 87 journals that published 87 articles, whereas the outlying zone contained 83 journals that published 83 articles. The distribution across 200 sources showed a precise concentration of articles in a relatively small

demonstrate the centrality of these concepts, whereas their high link strengths indicate their pivotal role in integrating related concepts. The clusters delineate the core research domains: virtual learning and delivery methods (red), immersive technologies such as augmented and virtual reality (green), higher education practices and learning contexts (blue), e-learning platforms and systems (yellow), learning management and pedagogical approaches (purple), and assessment tools with virtual learning environments (light blue). This analysis contributes significantly to understanding the field's structure by mapping interconnected technological domains and identifying emerging research directions, particularly regarding the integration of immersive technologies and pandemic-influenced educational adaptations.

Figure 7. Keywords density visualization map

Source: Output of Key words Co -occurrence analysis using VOS viewer software

Figure 7 shows the keyword density visualization map, which reveals the intensity and clustering patterns of the research terms in the field, with color gradients indicating the term frequency and prominence. Yellow font and larger font sizes indicate the most frequently occurring keywords. The density of yellow decreased when the frequency of occurrence of the keywords decreased. Furthermore, keyword-density visualization map, the co-occurrence of keywords is recognized by their proximity to each other. The analysis demonstrates strong centrality around the "virtual learning environment" as the dominant core concept, followed by "e-learning" as another highly significant term, indicated by their bright yellow-green coloration. Smaller clusters emerge around terms such as "augmented reality," "virtual reality," "learning management system," and "blended learning," which represent key technological subdomains. The density visualization also highlights significant interconnections between educational technology terms, with notable linkages around "higher education," "learning analytics," "pedagogy," and "Moodle," forming both central and peripheral clusters. The mapping reveals a combination of established research themes, such as virtual learning environments, and new intersections in areas such as learning analytics and virtual reality, demonstrating evolving technological integration patterns in educational environments.

Figure 8 illustrates the trending topics in Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) systems, with topic data spanning 2008 to 2024.

Larger blue-filled circles indicate higher frequencies and smaller circles indicate lower frequencies. Terms such as 'e-learning, virtual learning environments,' and 'computer-aided instruction' appeared with the highest frequencies of usage, signifying that they were the main topics in the field. Learning environments, ", and "computer-aided instruction" demonstrated the highest frequencies, marking them as prominent topics within the field. This analysis reveals some

established and emerging areas of VLE research. In the middle timeline, the topics "students" and "education" are found, which are consistent in VLE adoption studies.

Figure 8. Trend topics map

Source(s): Output of Biblioshiny software

More recent topics, such as "pandemic" (2020–2021), "virtual reality" (2021–2024), and "augmented reality" (2022–2024), along with "simulation training" and "computer simulation" (both 2022–2024), represent the newest research directions, likely influenced by technological advancements and global disruptions, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. These trending topics are potential areas for future research on VLE adoption. Based on this trending topic analysis, these frequently occurring themes can be considered potential priorities for future research on VLE systems. The high frequency of core areas, coupled with a clear temporal progression from basic concepts such as "online systems" (2010) to advanced technological integration (2024), suggests a research trajectory that emphasizes technological innovation, instructional creativity, and learner-centered experiences in virtual learning environments.

Figure 9. Thematic map of keywords

Source(s): Output of Biblioshiny software

A thematic map of the keywords is shown in Figure 9. It visually represents the relationships and trends among research themes in a particular field. It categorizes keywords and topics based on their frequency and co-occurrence in scientific literature and identifies significant

research areas. This mapping allowed us to identify emerging trends, core themes, and literature gaps and to better understand the research landscape (Dastani et al., 2024), as shown in the bibliometric analysis.

A thematic map is also produced that offers a structured and compact view of the VLE research landscape by grouping topics into Motor, Niche, Basic or Emerging or Declining themes according to their relevance (centrality) and development (density). Areas of robust, influential, and well-established in VLE research are represented by motor themes such as "human," "virtual learning environment," "virtual reality," "article," "humans," and "coronavirus disease 2019" which have high centrality and density. These themes illustrate how human-centric and technologically developed systems, considering the COVID-19 pandemic, have influenced VLE systems. Other niche themes are "total quality management," "telehealth," "gamification," "aged," and "depression," which represent highly specialized research areas with great development but low general relevance and are thus applicable to the context of healthcare education or mental well-being. Foundational elements of high centrality but low density were basic themes, including "e-learning," "virtual learning environments," "computer aided instruction," "students," and "teaching."

These topics are important for understanding the essential elements of VLE systems and their regular incorporation into broader educational research. On the other hand, emerging or declining themes like "education," "artificial intelligence," and "technology" or "academic achievement" might emerge or become irrelevant in the future. Although themes surrounding artificial intelligence and technology suggest closer ties between education and cutting-edge tools, academic achievement could show signs of a lack of attention in recent research. This analysis offers a strategic overview of the VLE research landscape, identifying established, specialized, foundational, and emerging research directions. It shows how VLE systems research has evolved and become more interdisciplinary and how such research can be most impactful in the future.

The following section discusses the implications of these findings in the field of VLE research, focusing mainly on the identified research gaps and future directions.

CONCLUSION

Trends in VLE adoption research are highlighted using bibliometric analysis. The field has grown significantly, with 14.61% annual publication growth between 2001 and 2024, and accelerated growth between 2017 and 2024. This growth also aligns with the increasing institutional adoption of virtual learning platforms, which has accelerated the COVID-19 pandemic. This influence is reflected in the surge in the number of publications from 2021 to 2022. However, the decline to 12 publications in 2023 and the subsequent recovery in 2024 may be associated with global disruptions or resource reallocation.

Thematic evolution from basic VLE implementation to advanced applications is a key finding. It consists of foundational research in virtual environments and learning systems (2001–2013), technology-enhanced instructional methods (2014–2020), and more recently, user-focused and integrated approaches (2021–2024), which include research in virtual reality (VR), behavioral research, and pedagogical effectiveness. This trajectory reflects the movement of the field away from infrastructure concerns regarding the city's use and teaching.

Geographic disparities in research impacts were revealed through citation analysis. However, the USA and the UK dominate publication volumes. At the same time, more minor contributors such as the Netherlands have a higher citation impact, implying that high-impact

research is about quality and methodological rigor rather than volume. These results underscore the importance of delivering innovation and rigour in balance in VLE studies.

Six clusters were identified using keyword co-occurrence analysis, with 'virtual learning environment' and 'learning' as the central nodes. Immersive technologies (VR/AR) and learning analytics are emerging as clusters with significant future potential. The emerging integration of social and psychological factors into VLE adoption is mirrored by behavioral themes.

This study has several limitations. The analysis was based solely on the Scopus database, which is a highly reputable source for bibliometric studies; however, this exclusive reliance may have excluded important publications in other databases (Amarathunga et al., 2024; Rejeb et al., 2022). Furthermore, keyword selection was used to determine the scope of the literature database by limiting the search to title, abstract, and keyword fields, which could have excluded relevant articles. Despite its transparency and objectivity, the method lacks transparency compared to traditional narrative review methods (Amarathunga et al., 2024; Hakala, 2010). To address these issues, future studies should use multiple databases, including the Web of Science, Google Scholar, IEEE, and ProQuest.

This study findings have several important implications. VLEs should be made as user-friendly as possible by institutions, immersive technology should be strategically invested in, and the technology developed should be compatible with teaching strategies. Future research should explore the integration of new technologies, test and validate teaching frameworks, and investigate regional differences through cross-cultural studies. Furthermore, there is a need for better methods of performance assessment for students and VLEs. It is also necessary to study in the long term how users adapt to these systems, how they accept them, and what barriers they find in different educational backgrounds.

In this regard, these insights seek to connect the dots among current and emerging themes to help advance the theoretical understanding and practical applications of VLEs in ways that point to directions for VLE research to be more in line with the emergent educational and technological demands.

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